

Determinants of the Community Empowerment Model through the P4GN Program to Realize a City Responding to Drug Threats In Cimahi City Indonesia

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Abstract

With the increasing importance of intellectual capital, the effective and efficient utilization of human potential within an organization has become a crucial competitive factor. Talent management, an advanced human resources practice that has gained significance in recent years in business organizations, focuses on the skills of employees. In this study, talent management practices aimed at selecting, employing, training, developing, and retaining talented candidates based on their skills in appropriate positions within the organization were examined, specifically in the banking sector. Hypotheses were formulated to investigate the impact of talent management practices in banks on employees' intention to leave. The data necessary to test the hypotheses were obtained through a survey applied to 421 bank employees in some provinces in Turkey. The survey results were analyzed using various statistical methods and testing techniques (frequency distribution, mean, T-test, ANOVA, correlation, and regression) by SPSS. A statistical significance level of $p < 0.05$ was accepted in all analyses. As a result of the analysis, it was founded that talent management has a significant correlation with the intention to leave. Consequently, the findings indicate that the implementation of talent management reduces the intention to leave, and evaluations and comments are made within this framework.

Keywords: Talent, Talent Management, Intention to Leave, Turnover Intention

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1. Introduction

Drug crime is a form of social humanitarian problem that is latent, dynamic, and transnational in dimension with the involvement of perpetrators who have an international network (Daulay). Drug crime is one of the problems of human civilization that must be dealt with seriously so that it does not develop more aggressively and destructively that can threaten the national resilience of a country (Hakim, 2023). In order to anticipate the dynamics and challenges of the aggressiveness of the threat of drug crime, the government needs to build and develop a comprehensive, integrative, and sustainable handling system by optimizing all available resources (Agustino, 2018). In the era of regional autonomy, apart from the 6 (six) areas of government affairs that are the responsibility of the central government, namely: foreign policy, defense, security, judiciary, national monetary and fiscal, and religion, district/city governments have a very important and strategic role in determining the direction of regional development. Although the issue of handling drug problems is included in the scope of the legal and security fields that are under the authority of the central government, it is undeniable that drug problems are closely related to other development fields, namely health, social, economic and education, which are included in the authority of the Regional Government (Oktavian, 2023). The role and contribution of Regional Governments is very important in efforts to handle drug problems in the region, because drug problems are complex and must involve cross-sectors of development (Ahmad, 2024).

Drug abuse, structuring healthy and safe residential areas, strengthening institutional and community capacity, and so on (Simanjuntak, 2017). Various efforts to improve the ability to anticipate, adapt, and mitigate various threats of drug crime in the region can be integrated with various regional development programs implemented by various sectors so that they have a chain impact on the success of various parties or sectors accompanied by the creation of community security (Eviany, 2023). The issue of public security has now been known as the concept of human security which is more focused on comprehensive security and is more multidimensional with security actors or objects that no longer solely rely on state security (state-centric) but also include people-centric security (Siagian, 2023). On the other hand, changes in the typology of threats also have an impact on the development of the concept of human security (Mukhtar, 2017). Threats that were originally only traditional and thick with military elements, have slowly expanded into non-traditional threats that include the issue of terrorism, human trafficking, illicit drug trafficking, food shortages, environmental degradation and so on. Some of these non-traditional threats have proven to have implications, either directly or indirectly, on basic human needs and survival

Based on the role and authority of the Regional Government, the handling of drug problems in the region can be directed to efforts to improve the ability to anticipate, adapt, and mitigate various threats of drug crimes that occur in the region. Improving regional capabilities can be achieved through strengthening leadership and good government management, strengthening regional policies that are responsive to the threat of drug crimes, and developing facilities or facilities for handling victims

The problem of drug abuse and illicit circulation is one of the major challenges faced by various cities in Indonesia, including Cimahi City (Gunawan, 2019). Drugs not only threaten the health and safety of individuals, but also have a negative impact on the social and economic stability of the community (Putri, 2024). Based on a report by the National Narcotics Agency (BNN) in 2023, the number of drug abuse cases in Indonesia continues to increase, with adolescents and youth being the most vulnerable. This condition requires more effective and integrated efforts in preventing, eradicating, and handling drug problems at the local level.

The P4GN (Prevention, Eradication, Abuse, and Illicit Circulation of Drugs) program is one of the strategic initiatives that has been implemented in various regions to overcome the drug problem (Antiprawiro, 2014). This program is designed with a comprehensive approach, including education, prevention, eradication, and rehabilitation for victims of drug abuse. However, the effectiveness of the P4GN Program is highly dependent on the active participation of the community and how the program is implemented at the community level (Fanagi, 2019). This is where the role of the community empowerment model becomes very important.

The community empowerment model in the context of the P4GN Program serves as a trigger for the success of the program. Community empowerment involves increasing the capacity of individuals and groups in dealing with drug threats, with the aim of building strong social resilience. By actively engaging the community, this model not only places them as beneficiaries, but also as key actors who play a role in drug prevention and control. This approach has been shown to be effective in various studies that show that community participation can significantly improve the outcomes of drug prevention and eradication programs.

Cimahi City, as one of the regions that has serious challenges related to drug abuse, has adopted the P4GN Program with a community empowerment approach. However, the extent to which this community empowerment model is successful and what factors affect its success still needs further research. Identifying the determinants that affect the effectiveness of this model is very important to strengthen the implementation of the P4GN Program in Cimahi City and can be used as a reference for other cities facing similar problems. This study aims to identify and analyze the factors that determine the success of the community empowerment model in the P4GN Program in Cimahi City. By understanding these factors, it is hoped that recommendations can be produced that can increase the effectiveness of the program and help realize Cimahi City as a city that is responsive, proactive, and resilient to drug threats.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative approach with a descriptive method that describes the phenomenon of Determinant Factors of the Community Empowerment Model through the P4GN program to realize a City to respond to drug threats in Cimahi City. Data collection was carried out by documentation studies, interviews, and participant observations (Fadili, 2023). The subjects of the study are managers, instructors, and participants or MSME actors. The stages of research carried out include 1) the pre-research stage, which is carried out to obtain information, data, and initial facts that will be the material for analysis to determine the direction of the research. At this

stage, it is carried out by selecting and determining the research problem, formulating the problem in the form of a research title, selecting and determining the location and subject of the research, formulating the research objectives and conducting a preliminary study. In addition, the formulation and submission of the draft research proposal was carried out at the pre-research stage. 2) implementation stage. At this stage, the researcher plays the role of the main instrument, which is tasked with collecting data by conducting research based on research supporting instruments including observation guidelines, interview guidelines, and several other guidelines. At this stage of implementation, the researcher technically carried out activities including: (1) determining the research subjects to be interviewed by paying attention to sampling techniques; (2) after determining the research subject, the researcher contacts the subject/educator to be interviewed; (3) conducting interviews with resource persons with reference to the interview guidelines that have been made; and (4) conducting observations and documentation studies that produce field notes in the form of descriptions of data obtained during the research. 3) the data analysis stage which is part of the process of processing data and facts that have been obtained during the research implementation process and is carried out when the collected data is completed. The analysis of the data and facts obtained is carried out by the process of preparation, categorization, association, and structuring of data objectively to achieve the goals in accordance with the plan that has been set. Furthermore, the stages of data analysis in accordance with the data analysis model used in this study include: (1) data collection; (2) data reduction; (3) data presentation; and (4) verification

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Description of Community Empowerment

Empowerment is an effort made to make individuals or groups in society empowered. Empowered here means the ability to do something to restore and/or improve the state of an individual or group. The history of the term empowerment began to emerge because of the situation of community groups that were discriminated against from the patriarchal development program policy. Such an understanding causes some community groups to become helpless, especially farmers and other helpless community groups. Because of such circumstances, the idea of developing to build balance in society emerged, especially in the financial aspect.

Suharto (2006, p.57) explained the meaning of constitutional empowerment, where empowerment comes from the word "power". Power is defined as power or power, which is the ability of an individual to do what he wants. This power is not because of power, power here in the sense that the individual has his own ability and/or potential that can be empowered. Another understanding comes from the opinion of Kartasasmita (1996, p.144) who explained community empowerment as an effort to improve the condition of the community so that they can be empowered and get out of the poverty chain. This aims to increase their dignity and dignity.

Empowerment is to provide an opportunity for a person to improve their knowledge and skills in order to develop the resource capacity of each individual (Jim Ife, 1995, p.182). This effort is carried out in order to influence the capacity of the community in the future, by involving the community itself to participate. Pearson added that the concept of empowerment emphasizes that

individuals need to improve their knowledge, skills, and power to improve their own qualities and take part in paying attention to others to learn as well.

David Korten (1993, hlm.56) mengemukakan pendapatnya mengenai pengertian pemberdayaan sebagai upaya dalam meningkatkan kemandirian rakyat, dengan tolok ukur kapasitas dan kekuatan internal masyarakat. Daya dukung baik material atau bahkan nonmaterial melalui redistribusi modal. Suharto (2006, hlm.68) menyebutkan beberapa prinsip pemberdayaan masyarakat sebagai berikut:

1. Pemberdayaan merupakan a collaborative process, therefore cooperation is needed.

2. The community is the subject and object in the empowerment process. They are seen as competent and have the ability to identify existing resources and opportunities.

3. The public must realize that they have an important role to play that will influence change

According to Suzzana Kindervater (1979, p.63) revealed empowerment as a person's effort to gain understanding and control, related to social, economic, and/or political aspects. In addition, he explained the role of non-formal education in the context of the empowerment process, namely:

1. It is not only about promoting the acquisition of information and skills.
2. Emphasizes the use of the ability to solve problems collaboratively
3. Oriented to the influence of socio-economic structures and relationships through group decision-making.
4. Topics related to aspects of health, literacy, or vocational skills, which place the importance of how the educational process supports relationships to learn students.
5. The designed program allows individuals or groups to critically analyze their own life situation and develop a mind of what skills are needed to act to improve their situation.

Suzzana Kindervater (1979, p.63) revealed that empowerment is a person's effort to gain understanding and control, related to social, economic, and/or political aspects. This understanding is carried out to be recognized for its position in society. The Inter America Foundation (IAF) formulates several indicators that mark the improvement of the position of the community, which are as follows:

1. *Access*, which is an increase in community opportunities in developing resources;
2. *Leverage*, i.e. the increase in bargaining positions collectively;
3. *Choices*, which is an increase in ability and opportunity to choose every option that is possible to choose.
4. *Status* (status), which is the increase in a condition in improving self-concept and positive cultural identity.

5. *Critical reflection capability*, which is an increase in the ability to solve problems by involving experiences experienced as an alternative to consideration;
6. *Legitimation*, which is to increase the ability to weigh every request of people fairly;
7. *Discipline*, which is the increased ability to be disciplined and work productively; and
8. *Creative perception*, which is the increase in the ability to think creatively and innovatively about the surrounding environmental conditions.

The above presentation concludes that community empowerment is an effort to improve the quality of life of a person or group by utilizing their potential and resources in their environment collaboratively. Empowerment cannot be done without the participation of the community itself because they are important actors in the empowerment process.

Determinants of the Community Empowerment Model through the P4GN Program to Realize a City Responding to Drug Threats in Cimahi City

In an effort to realize a Cimahi City that is responsive to drug threats, the community empowerment model through the P4GN Program (Drug Prevention, Eradication, Abuse, and Illicit Circulation) plays a very important role. The success of this program is greatly influenced by several determinants that determine how effectively this empowerment model can be implemented and achieve the desired results. The following are the determinants that play a role in the success of the community empowerment model through the P4GN Program in Cimahi City:

1. Active Community Participation: Community participation is the key to the success of the empowerment model in the P4GN Program. The level of awareness and community involvement in drug prevention and eradication activities determines the effectiveness of the program. Active participation includes involvement in socialization, training, and drug cadres and anti-drug posts at the village level. The higher the community participation, the stronger the social resilience that is formed, so that it can minimize the spread and impact of drugs.

2. Training and Capacity Building of Cadres: The success of the P4GN Program is also greatly influenced by the quality of training and capacity building of anti-drug cadres. Well-trained cadres will have the knowledge, skills, and effective strategies to carry out socialization, early detection, and intervention against drug abuse cases in their communities. Comprehensive and continuous training ensures that cadres can carry out their roles optimally and become effective agents of change in society.

3. Cross-Sectoral Collaboration: Collaboration factors between various stakeholders, such as local governments, law enforcement officials, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), schools, and the private sector, are an important element in the community empowerment model. This collaboration creates synergies that allow the P4GN program to be carried out in a more integrated and effective manner. With strong support and cooperation between institutions, this program can be more accessible to the community and have a wider impact.

4. Existence and Function of Anti-Drug Posts: Anti-drug posts in each sub-district function as a center for information, coordination, and services for the community related to drug prevention and control. The post plays an important role in raising public awareness, providing consultation services, and being a place to report suspicious activity. The existence of an active and well-functioning post is one of the important determinants in the success of the community empowerment model through the P4GN Program.

5. Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation: Monitoring and evaluation conducted periodically is essential to assess the effectiveness of the community empowerment model and the P4GN program. Through the evaluation process, areas that need improvement can be identified and strategic adjustments can be made to ensure that the program is running in accordance with the objectives. The evaluation also serves as a tool to measure the impact of the program and ensure that the long-term goal of creating a drug-free Cimahi City, can be achieved.

4. CONCLUSION

This study emphasizes that the community empowerment model through the P4GN Program (Prevention, Eradication, Abuse, and Illicit Circulation of Drugs) has a crucial role in realizing a Cimahi City that is responsive to drug threats. The success of this program is greatly influenced by the active participation of the community, the effectiveness of training and strengthening the capacity of anti-drug cadres, as well as cross-sector collaboration involving the government, law enforcement officials, NGOs, schools, and the private sector. The existence of anti-drug posts in each village has also proven to be an important factor in supporting public awareness and increasing the effectiveness of the program. Continuous monitoring and evaluation are needed to ensure that the program is running according to its objectives, as well as to identify and improve areas that still need attention. By optimizing these factors, the P4GN Program can be more effective in creating a Cimahi City that is free from drug abuse and has strong social resilience.

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